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Apprenticeship In Igbo Land And Venture Success In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

This study investigate Apprenticeship in Igbo Land and venture success in Anambra State. The study specifically Determine the effect of seed capital, mentorship and apprenticeship training system, on venture success in Anambra State Relevant conceptual, theoretical and empirical literature were reviewed. The study is anchored on skill acquisition theory. Survey research design was adopted in this study. The sources of data in this study were primary and secondary sources. The population for the study comprised 4212 population. The sample size of 809 was determined by using the Borg & Gall formular. The instrument use for data collection was questionnaire. The adopted content validity and the reliability of the instrument was maintained through the test-retest method and spearman's rank correlation coefficient. The coefficient of reliability was found to be high, $R_s=0.79394$. Statistics such as frequency count and percentages was put to use in the analysis of research questions while hypotheses was tested using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) analysis. The hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance. The regression result shows that seed capital has significant effect on venture success in Anambra State; mentorship has significant effect on venture success in Anambra State and apprenticeship training system has significant effect on venture success in Anambra State. The study concluded that apprenticeship in Igbo Land had a positive significance effect on venture success in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study recommended that there is need for adequate regulations on the seed capital for the Igbo apprenticeship system by involving government and financial institutions. There should be more regulations in this scheme to provide adequate legal framework to guide and regulate the scheme. Stakeholders should equally support successfully graduated apprentices to gain a foothold in their new business by providing more training and finance to establish more business and entrepreneurial ventures instead of looking for paid and salaried employment. Apprentices should continually undergo more appropriate traditional and formal business training to obtain necessary skills and experiences. Government and educational institutions should make the scheme formal by incorporating it into school and educational curriculum.

Keywords: Seed Capital, Mentorship, Apprenticeship Training System, Venture Success

INTRODUCTION

Generations of people have transferred skills from one generation to another in some form of apprenticeship. In Nigeria and all over Africa, apprenticeship has been an age long method of training young people in trade and craft, agriculture, business and catering. When youths in olden days achieved the status of skilled workers; they became important members of the society. In Igbo land, apprenticeship system was an institution that was generally guarded by customs, lineage and rituals. Every male born into a family was expected to learn his patrilineal and

matrilineal craft, and it was easy to identify a young male child as a member of a particular lineage found to be proficient in the lineage craft. The apprenticeship system was brought to the limelight in Nigeria after the Nigerian-Biafran war. Many parents who were left with nothing after the war were forced to send their children (8-20 years) to learn trade to survive as traders. This was how Igbo settlers after the war rebuilt Onitsha, Nnewi, Aba and most parts of Lagos. Some opine that the apprentice scheme among the Igbos contributed immensely to their survival after the Nigeria civil war

In the apprenticeship system, the 'Oga' (master or Boss) and 'Nwaboyi' (servant or apprentice) are in agreement for a period ranging from 4-7 years (and sometimes longer) whereby the apprentice is to serve and learn from the 'Oga'. Usually, the mode of settlement is contained in the agreement. Apprenticeship as a method of establishing young people, and training the unskilled, has been very beneficial to the Igbos. Many people achieved excellence in their calling because their Oga trained and settled them well in the trade they learnt. Many notable business moguls in Onitsha, Nnewi and many parts of Igbo land attribute their success to what they learnt as apprentice. Admittedly, apprenticeship offers the 'Nwaboyi' the opportunity to acquire business acumen, work attitude and ethics on how to deal with suppliers and customers, and interaction with other practitioners and colleagues. It provides contacts/networks and lessens the burden on the Nwaboyi's parents. In addition, it has helped youths from indigent homes to achieve financial success and excellence in what they do. The importance of Apprenticeship in rural economy cannot be overemphasized as they have been identified as a veritable vehicle for employment generation, poverty reduction, indigenous technology, reduce the flow of people from rural to urban areas, increase the gross domestic earning etc. at low investment rate as well as the development of capabilities (Obananya 2022). It is obvious on the way some countries have encouraged the entrepreneurs sector, thus reducing the level of unemployment to the barest minimum. In every economy both develop and developing economy, one cannot rule out the importance of entrepreneurs. Apprenticeship is one the measures embraced by the government to reduce mass poverty and unemployment in the country. This study is not established to evaluate past measures of poverty reduction in Nigeria, but aim at investigating the effect of entrepreneurship training on poverty alleviation (Obananya 2022).

The Igbo Apprentice and Apprenticeship programme have been given diverse explanations by various schools of thoughts and scholars (Nzewi, Onwuka, & Onyesom, 2017). The programme entails more of engaging individual or a person that has decided to embark and learn a specific skill or job by working for a fixed period of time, for someone who is very good at that job or skill (Inyang, & Agwadu, 2017). The Apprentice can be a teenager or young person, male or female that embarks on learning or receiving practical training skills, and also sometimes theoretical knowledge in a specialized area of vocation, trade or occupation he/she has chosen to trade on for a period of time. And for apprenticeship, some have suggested that it is an effective mechanism for easy learning transition for young people to move from school base approach to the world of work or other tasks associated with such (Olulu, & Udeorah, 2018). The other way round, the apprenticeship generally has been described as dedicated and enabling form of vocational education (technical, vocational, or artificial intelligence) combining both job learning and school-based training for specifically defined competences, skills, capacities and work processes (Olusegun, & Olanrewaju, 2017). This should be regulated by law and based on written patterns of employment and contract with a reward system or payments, and standards that operates with social protection scheme. More often, issuance of certificate and dedicated recognition follows the expiration of training where relevant certificates, licensing are awarded to successful apprenticeship fellows. A critical look at the following explanations of apprenticeship somehow does not speak directly to the Igbo style of apprenticeship program, however, certain elements and features are shared in them. The Igbo type as it is currently does not have any affiliation to schools, universities or colleges, though this is where we aim in the nearest future from now. The Igbo apprenticeship model and programme is the brain behind the existing and consistent operations of small scale businesses across Igbo land (Diyoke, 2014).. The Igbo Apprenticeship programme and activities have been observed to be a sine qua non for the economy of Nigeria and the quality of life of the people at both rural and urban settings Apprenticeship is a system for training a new generation of practitioners of a trade or profession with on-the-job training.

Apprenticeships can also enable practitioners to gain a license to practice in a regulated occupation (Fajobi, Olatujoye, Amusa, & Adedoyin. (2017).

Most of their training is done while working for an employer or master who helps the apprentices learn their trade or profession, in exchange for their continued labor for an agreed period after they have achieved measurable competencies. Apprenticeship lengths vary significantly across sectors, professions, roles and cultures. In some cases people who successfully complete an apprenticeship can reach the "journeyman" or professional certification level of competence. Olulu & Udeorah (2018) posits that apprenticeship may be considered as a system of learning whereby an individual trained in a professional skill in a practical way through a structured programme of on-the-job training. It usually involves acquiring knowledge, technical skills and the development of an attitude or discipline for a particular job. Orugun & Nafiu (2014) opine that apprenticeship provides a ladder of opportunity to obtain critical skills. Businesses require flourishing, placing apprenticeship as the seedbed of entrepreneurship. He further stated that the combination of these attributes, the business and entrepreneurial activities of the Igbos continue to be the backbone of commerce and manufacturing in the Nigerian economy. The apprenticeship practice is in three categories viz; the traditional model, the informal model and the modern apprenticeship model. The traditional model involves the transfer of family skill to the next generation of members, while the informal model though traditional in nature, have non-family members engage in the apprenticeship scheme. The modern apprenticeship scheme involves training of participants in vocational skills, well structured programme of learning, fixed working/training hours and combination of vocational training with educational programmes. In Nigeria, the practice of apprenticeship is popular among the Nupes, Igbos, Fulanis and other tribes that have specialised skills which they pass on from generation to generation. Trades in apprenticeship category in Nigeria includes; blacksmith, welding, trading, block molding, motor mechanics and repair, barbing, electronics repair, wood carving amongst others.

Expatriated further that apprenticeship may also take the form of helping new employees to relate their previous education to the requirement of their new job. Apprenticeship also incorporates a system of guidance and counseling as most apprentices are required to live with their masters so as to acquire through a process of acculturation the necessary altitude, diplomacy and decorum required for the job. It is the combination of these depositions that make graduates of apprenticeship training entrepreneurs instead of job seekers (Anyanwu, 2011; Craig and Bittel, 2017). The apprenticeship system practiced among the Igbo ethnic group is arranged in such a way that the apprentice lives with his master so as to acquire through a process of acculturation the necessary attitude, diplomacy and decorum required for the trade or skill acquisition, usually for an agreed number of years after which the master settles the apprentice by setting up a business for him, that is provision of startup capital and the required guidance up until certain level of business maturity. Analysts have described the Igbo apprenticeship system that governs their entrepreneurship development as the largest business incubator platform in Africa and perhaps in the world. It is the combination of these dispositions that make graduates of Igbo apprenticeship scheme entrepreneurs instead of job seekers. It is therefore imperative to carry out the study of this magnitude to substantiate the assertion (Alike & Umunze, 2019).

Gumbari in Mshelia (2019) asserts that skill acquisition in Nigeria should be perceived as a catalyst to increase the rate of economic growth, create job opportunities, reduce import of manufactured goods and decrease trade deficits that result from such import. Ezeji and Okorie as cited in Nwanaka and Amaehule (2011) assert that while stressing the importance of skill acquisition in national growth, emphatically contended, "that Nigeria's social and economic problems will be drastically reduced if people are given adequate vocational training in skills, raw materials, machineries and equipment". It is only with skilled men that materials can be harnessed, manipulated and transformed into products with quality skill acquisition programme.

Statement of the Problem

The Igbo apprentice system is an extension of their entrepreneurial make-up where a strategic training process is utilized to train mostly young men of igbo stock into entrepreneurial ventures by established

entrepreneurs locally known as Oga, (Ejo-Orusa2019). This venture can be a trade, an enterprise or a vocation, in some cases serving also as a domestic help. The Ogas are former apprentices that had served and were settled with seed capitals to begin their own enterprises (Alike & Umunze 2019). This system is informal, and has unstructured training programs to learn and master skills required to embark on own enterprise, Dishonesty on the part of the Master or the apprentice has tended to dent the good intentions of the Nwaboi apprenticeship system. Myraids of problem confront this apprentice system, one of which has been observed that towards the expiration of the agreed apprenticeship period in some cases, masters accuse the apprentices of frivolous crimes and send them away just to avoid their contractual obligations and thus deprive them of the settlement entitlements. The traditional apprenticeship system in Nigeria involves hardship, discipline and loyalty especially on the part of the apprentice (Adekola& Ezekiel, 2013). This is the case particularly where payment is not made by the apprentice. The apprentice is therefore expected to serve the master in different capacities in domestic duties as a 'houseboy'. Yet again is the inadequate legal framework to guide the system. This is possibly the most critical challenge of the Nwaboi apprenticeship system. Although the Contract of Apprenticeship in Nigeria is regulated by the Labour Act 2004, it has been contended that the system is a far cry from what is obtainable in other countries in terms of mode of operation, regulation, rewards, structure and implementation.

Objectives of the Study

The general purpose of this study is to investigate the Apprenticeship in Igbo Land and venture success in Anambra State. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine the effect of seed capital on venture success in Anambra State
2. Assess the effect of mentorship on venture success in Anambra State
3. Examine the effect of apprenticeship training system, on venture success in Anambra State

Research Questions

Based on the specific objectives, the following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

What is the effect of seed capital on venture success in Anambra State?

To what extent does mentorship affect venture success in Anambra State?

What is the effect of apprenticeship training system, on venture success in Anambra State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the objectives of the study and strengthen the analysis:

Ho: Seed capital has no significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

Ho: Mentorship has no significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

Ho: Apprenticeship training system has no significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Apprenticeship

When someone learns a skill under the tutelage of another, it could be said to be the act of undergoing apprenticeship. So, apprenticeship has to do with the act of learning something from someone more knowledgeable and experienced in the area concerned. Aligning with this definition, Adekola (2013) posits that apprenticeship is the process of learning/skill acquisition through enlistment with a master craftsman. It is a system of training a new generation of practitioners of a structured competence, a basic set of skills (Werner and Desimone, 2016). Hence, for something to be termed an apprenticeship scheme, it has to be knowledge or skill cantered. That is, someone must be learning something while another is responsible for teaching. At the beginning of any apprenticeship, there is always an agreement. The agreement could be formal or informal agreement, that is, the apprentice or their parents or guardian may come to terms with the master or the representative about the duration and terms of the agreement.

Obananya (2022) stated that basically, apprenticeship involves a contractual relationship between a master craftsman and a trainee. Apprenticeship training which is basic practice of starting a business in order to earn profit on new found opportunities can go a long way to stabilise economy of a nation as well

as generate massive returns to the government. Apprenticeship training can impact the economy of a country in diverse ways. It is through entrepreneurship that important innovations enter the markets leading to new product or production process which eventually increases efficiency by bringing competition into the market. It contributes to poverty reduction when it creates employment through the start-up of new business or the expansion of existing ones and they increase social wealth by markets, new technology, new jobs and increase in real productivity, increase income which culminates in higher standard of living for the people. Apprenticeship is the heart of any country's economy and a country that does not play with its entrepreneurs has better chance of an improved economy. Many areas of endeavour require apprenticeship training to be an expert therein. Some of the areas where apprenticeship is involved include blacksmith, welding, trading, block molding, motor mechanics and repair, barbing, electronics repair, catering, baking among others (Olulu & Udeorah, 2018). The Igbo apprenticeship system is a system of apprenticeship where a master agrees to train another person; this training comes in different forms. Some come at no cost to the apprentice, this is called "Igba-boi". In Igba-boi, the apprentice learns a line of trade and comes to live with the master, the master takes care of the needs of the apprentice during the duration of the agreement, and the apprentices, in turn, helps out the master in other areas apart from the training business.

The agreement period here is usually varied between 4-8 years and in some cases more years. At the end of the agreed period, the master settles the apprentice and the trainee sets out to establish a business for himself or teams up with the master. Olulu and Udeorah (2018) state that in Igba-boi, the family of the apprentice does not pay any fee for the training and at the agreement, the trainee (apprentice) is allowed to establish his own. Another form of Igbo apprenticeship is "imu ahia" (learning trade) or "imu oru" (learning a craft or hand work). In the former, the apprentice learns a trade at a fee, while in the later, the apprentice learns a skill or handiwork, a fee is also attached to it. The agreement period in these types is usually shorter than what is obtained in Igba-boi. In this system, the apprentice pays a premium or a training fee to the trainer (master) (Crescent, 2019). In differentiating imu-olu or imu-ahia with igba-boi, Olulu and Udeorah (2018) opine that unlike Igba-boi where mentees arrange a contract to have a complete training circle for free, imu-oru or imu-ahia is not done for free. In this, the apprentice is expected to pay a fee to their master to acquire skills. The contract lasts for a shorter period in comparison with igba-boi. The Igbo Igba-boi model is a process whereby someone is being trained in the act of entrepreneurship at no cost (Agozino & Anyanike, 2017) while imu-ahia entails training in the act of entrepreneurship, but at a cost to the trainee.

Seed Capital: Pandey (2015) defines seed capital as an innovation of significance in the twentieth century, a synonym of risk capital, and a source of finance for early stage enterprise for start up and young enterprise seeking to grow rapidly. OECD (2014) defines it as a capital provided by firms who invest alongside management in young companies that are not quoted on the stock exchange market. Unpaid business Apprenticeship designated as the incubator model allows people to learn business from a master for certain duration and at the end of the apprenticeship period, get seed capital and support from the master to start up his own business. According to Kanu (2019) Keuschnigg and Nielsen (2010), seed capital has come to specialize in financing early stage investment, supply equity finance and provides valuable business advice to enhance SMEs survival. From the above definitions, venture capital differs from conventional form of financing due to the following: (i) provision of equity through purchase of share, options and convertible securities directly with the objective of disposing-off once the business is profitable (ii) Long-term investment spanning between 5-10 years not repayable on demand at the option of the venture capitalists (iii) involvement of providers of funds in management thereby rendering support services such as marketing, recruitment of key personnel and designing strategies. (Heard & Sibert, 2010; EVCA, 2014; Kumar, 2015).

Seed capital financing is a form of financing that is employed to finance a relatively small size companies/ firms before they can be qualified for public underwriting (Ariyo, 2010). Seed capital is an important financial market intermediary that provides capital to small and young firms that have difficulties in attracting financing (Bonini and Capizzi, 2019). They often finance a firm in the early stage

of development of the business. Hence, there are different kinds of seed capital available for different stages of business development (Solomon, 2016). These types of seed capital include seed capital, start-up capital and development capital among others. Most of the firms that require seed capital financing faces a lot of uncertainties, operate in a dynamic market environment and often, own little tangible assets (Sahlman, 2010).

Seed capital organizations finance these potentially but higher risky ventures by purchasing equity stakes (Kaplan and Strömberg, 2013). The seed capital not only possess the equity of the venture but also come up with various strategies to overcome the challenges that emerge at each stage of the investment process. Normally, the seed capital must pass through certain circle which starts from raising a seed fund and then, proceeds through the investment (Gompers, 2016). To ensure profitability of the business, monitoring and value addition to firms is essential. When the business turns out to be successful, the venture capital firm exits successful deals and returns capital to its investors, (Groot, 2019).

Mentoring: Mentoring is fast gaining momentum as a very effective approach of human resource development in organizations all around the world. Mentoring is one way for companies to help since it fosters a high degree of trust and mutual respect, allowing mentees to become who they want to be by realizing their potential. Mentoring is widely recognized as a vital part of growing organizational capability. However, the awareness that both the mentor and the mentee require each other's collaboration for the organization's success is what makes mentoring work successfully in the workplace (Eze, Muogbo and Obananya, 2021). The mentoring relationship is at its finest when both the mentor and the mentee join the relationship freely. Mentorship and business growth provide a variety of advantages, including wellbeing, satisfaction, development, progress, and feeling rejuvenated in professional advancement, acquiring new technologies, and being aware of key company challenges, methods, strategies, or views. Mentoring has been identified as a powerful tool for professional growth in both the public and commercial sectors (Eze, Muogbo and Obananya, 2021). Mentoring programs and relationships can fail for a variety of reasons, including a lack of commitment, leadership involvement, poor planning, unrealistic expectations, and unclear goals. Mentoring involves a process that brings together inexperienced and experienced individuals in an attempt to enable the former to gain knowledge, self-confidence, skills as the other benefits from the later as they transit through the process. Allen (2017) posits that mentoring is a system of semi-structured guidance where one person or a group of people share their knowledge, skills, and experience to assist others in progressing in their own lives and careers. Eze, Muogbo and Obananya, 2021) states that mentorship involves a formal or informal training partnership where employees receive information, advice, and guidance from an experienced professional, usually within the organization, who has expertise and a motivation to help others grow in their jobs. , mentorship involves a process that brings together the inexperienced and the experienced in an attempt where the former will gain knowledge, self-confidence, skills and competencies from the later as they transit through the process (Colky and Young, 2016) .

Mentorship further involves motivating and empowering the other person to identify their own issues and goals, and helping them to find ways of resolving or reaching them. It is not by doing it for them, or expecting them to 'do it the way I did it', but by understanding and respecting different ways of working (Bozionelos, 2016). There are essentially two major types of mentoring – informal and formal. Informal, also known as traditional or natural mentoring represents the default model of mentorship. According to Freedman (2019), the informal mentoring relationship is one that happens spontaneously based on mutual respect, rapport and relationship. On the other hand, formal mentoring is organized by the organization. Formal mentoring makes “mentorship a systemic policy issue and a standard part of management practice,” (Ehrich & Hansford, 2012)

Apprenticeship Training System: Training is a means of human capacity building in an institution that is specially designed to entrance efficiency and morale of the employee at work. It is a programme targeted at improving staff knowledge, skills and attitude (KSA) at work so as to remove any form of deficiency in job performance and misconduct at work (Abiola, 2017).) Training is an institutional effort aimed at helping an employee acquire basic skills required for the efficient execution of the function for

which he was hired is said to narrow to specific target. Training can be described as a form of teaching and/or practice application in the realm of development of skills (Adekoya, & Adetoro, 2017). Igbo apprenticeship training system is unstructured and informal, with training done on the job while the masters delegate authority to the most senior apprentice (oldest Apprentice) who in turn delegates part of the authority to the next apprentice down the line. Alike and Orjiako Umunze (2019) state that in the system which is informal, there is scheduled agreed time frame which an Apprentice undergoes in order to acquire a desirable aspect of entrepreneurial skill. Apprentices do not earn salaries during the apprenticeship period but their masters give them, food, clothing, accommodation and transport in some cases. According to Chinweuba and Ezenwa (2017) the Apprentices work for the Masters, after completion of training for an agreed period of time. On completion the apprentice stewardship is evaluated by the Master who settles the apprentice with cash or goods or rent payment for business premises or a combination of any two or the three. This principle which is fundamental practice creates long-lasting mutual trust and love between the Master(s) and Apprentice(s). The Apprentice is appraised by the following factors- work ethics, respect for Master, customers, performance of domestic chores, development of social and business skills. Hence, the Igbo apprenticeship training system is all embracing in developing an individual.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Skill Acquisition Theory Dekeyser (2007). The fundamental claim of Skill Acquisition Theory, as per Dekeyser (2007), "is that the learning of a wide variety of skills shows an exceptional similarity in development from introductory representation of knowledge through starting changes in conduct to eventual fluent, unconstrained, to a great extent, and profoundly gifted behaviour, and that this phenomena can be accounted for by a lot of essential principles regular to acquisition of skills". Overall, as referenced by Speelman (2005), skill acquisition can be considered as a particular type of learning, where learning has been characterized as "the representation of information in memory concerning some natural or psychological event". Thusly, as indicated by him, skill acquisition is a type of learning where "skilled behaviours can become routinized and even programmed under certain conditions". What's more, as a general theory of learning, it guarantees that an adult starts learning something through largely unequivocal procedures, and with subsequent adequate practice and exposure, move into verifiable procedures. Subsequently, the study is hinged on this theory.

Empirical Review

Orogbu, Onyeizugbe and Onuzulike-Chukwuemeka (2021) determine the extent to which start-up capital, business skill, tenure of apprenticeship, mentorship and business tolerance has influence survival rate among Igbo traders. The questionnaire was used for collection of data on a sample of 348 respondents drawn from two major markets in southeast Nigeria using multi-staged sampling technique. Data collected were analyzed using t-test statistics and the linear regression model. Findings revealed that start-up capital, business skills, tenure of apprenticeship, mentoring, business tolerance and financial discipline has a direct and positive relationship with survival rate among Igbo traders in South East, Nigeria. However, from the hypothesis tested, it was revealed that all the variable construct - start-up capital, mentoring, business skills, tenure of apprenticeship and business tolerance have significant influence on the survival rate among Igbo traders in South East, Nigeria. Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made: To ensure that start-up capital are dully provided to apprentice, parents and representative of the apprentice should ensure a legally documented agreement between the master and the apprentice. Parents and representatives of the apprentice should advise their ward on the need to be patient and diligent to carefully learn the business skills from the master because this is the basis for apprenticeship.

Ekesiobi and Dimnwobi (2020) investigated of the entrepreneurship practice of the *Igbos* of South-Eastern Nigeria. It is intended to deepen entrepreneurial development and employment generation in the country. This study also provides empirical support to situate the Igbo entrepreneurship model (IEM)

among existing entrepreneurship literature, particularly for research in developing countries. The study adopts a quantitative approach to examine 1187 responses carefully drawn from the Onitsha and Nnewi business clusters in Anambra state. In addition to descriptive demonstrations, the Propensity Score Matching (PSM) technique is employed to estimate the effects of treatment on the treated by pairing treatment and control units with similar attributes on the propensity score and other likely covariates. Specifically, the PSM is used to perform a counterfactual analysis of the effect of the entrepreneurship model on business outcomes by examining participants and non-participants in the IEM. The key findings of the study indicate that entrepreneurs who participated in the IEM have higher business survival rate, business growth rate and access to trade and informal credit, while non-IEM entrepreneurs have better access to formal credit source than the IEM graduates. Generalization of results can be limited since the study is based on responses of samples drawn from two clusters (Onitsha and Nnewi) in Anambra State, South-East Nigeria. The novelty of this study rests on its pioneering attempt to empirically examine how the IEM can drive entrepreneurial development in Nigeria. We also distil lessons for evidenced-based replication of the model to provide a sustainable employment channel for the country. The study posits, among other things, that the IEM can be a veritable approach for enterprise development and youth employment in Nigeria.

Ezeajughu, (2021) examined the Igbo man perspectives of apprenticeship and entrepreneurial development in southeast Nigeria. Through an apprenticeship scheme known as Igba-boi or Nwaobi which is by far the most entrenched and vibrant entrepreneurship promotion vehicle in Nigeria, people from this ethnic group have dominated and continued to excel above their contemporaries from other ethnic groups in the country and beyond. This paper analytically investigates peculiar sources, circumstances and skills that are the fulcrum of increasing socio-economic performance of the Igbo people. The study finds that entrepreneurial performance of the Igbos is underscored by their economic culture and value, which are highly existential in their traditions and belief system. These are however fostered by the long years of marginalization by successive Nigerian governments, as well as other prominent factors in pre and post independence Nigeria. The paper concludes that the Nwa-boi Apprenticeship System has the potential to significantly increase the level of entrepreneurial metabolism and to stimulate the rate and pace of new venture creation and thus a viable platform for entrepreneurship promotion in Nigeria. The research also concludes that with this progressive rate, Igbo people will in time be a force to reckon with in the socio-political and techno-economic sector of Nigeria, Africa and the World at large. The study recommends that the government of Nigeria and African by extension should adopt the practice of the Igbo man apprenticeship system and entrepreneurial development in southeast Nigeria as a strategy for the development African entrepreneurship.

Okeke and Osang (2021) examined Igbo apprenticeship scheme in Anambra state. Its potency as it was, as it is and will be. The principal motivations of the scheme are the seed capital and mentorship given to the apprentices at the end of their indentureship and generation of employment in the state. But, the potency of the scheme is perceived to be waning. The study therefore seeks to interrogate the perceived decline of the potency of the scheme, utilizing the observation method in informal workplaces and trading sites spread across the state. The study discovered that, the unwillingness of young men to take up the businesses of their fathers, study courses that will promote their growth and malicious stealing of their masters money by the apprentices are key factors that led to the decline of the scheme's potency and the study therefore recommended that young men should key into family businesses so as to promote the heritage of business sustainability being transferred from generation to generation. Again, there should be a well- defined contractual agreement rather than oral agreement between the masters and the intending apprentices so as to protect the job creation intent of the scheme.

Adesola (2019) examined the relationships between the compensation-tied apprenticeship practice and employment generation among the Ibo businessmen in Osun state with a view to determine a sustainable way of propagating a viable business which will invariably reduce the level of unemployment in the Nation Primary data were extensively used for this study and Simple percentage Method with Analysis of Variance used to analysis the collected data.. Three businesses namely- electrical goods, mobile phone

accessories and motor parts were randomly selected and the sampled businesses were examined base on capacity building and continuity of the apprentices in this method of apprenticeship. The findings of the study revealed that majority 92% of the apprentices that are trained under this method of compensation-tied apprenticeship continued in the business they learnt while only 24% of those that learnt under other forms of apprenticeships continued in the business. The p-value of (0.0001) as against P-value of 0.00062 showed that compensation- tied apprenticeships are more reliable and viable in reducing unemployment rates in the study area. The study therefore concludes that compensation-tied type of apprenticeships would reduce unemployment palaver if given adequate attentions. In Nigeria

Emejulu, Idigo and Onyekwelu (2020) examined the causes of this dying trend in Southeast and proffer solutions. The concept of apprenticeship was examined, along with the unique Igbo apprenticeship system. Also, the role of apprenticeship in skill acquisition and job creation was examined. This study adopted a survey research design. The study area is southeast Nigeria, with the study covering five states of the region. The population was 500. The source of data for the study was a structured questionnaire. The method of data analysis was purely descriptive; using a combination of mean and frequencies. The study concluded that the unprecedented unemployment statistics in Nigeria can only get worse in the aftermath of the Coronavirus pandemic, and therefore the need to encourage youths to embrace apprenticeship as a viable way forward. Among others, the study recommended that the government should partner private organizations for a public- private arrangement to create more modern apprenticeship centres suited for the 21st-century economy.

Nkemdili, (2020) interrogate the practice and direction of Igbo apprenticeship, with particular interest in unravelling the reasons for the declining interest in apprenticeship generally among Igbo youths in South East, Nigeria. The paper is an exploratory, qualitative research paper premised on desk research encapsulating a comprehensive review of ethnographic and historical records while also utilizing the observation method in informal workplaces and trading sites spread across diverse work settings. The findings indicate that the much talked about Igbo apprenticeship is facing significant challenges, and several factors have combined to demarket Igbo apprenticeship, making it less appealing to unemployed youths, with grave implications for unemployment, wealth creation and poverty reduction. Given the demand of the modern labour market, the paper calls for a hybrid model of apprenticeship that introduces in a more systematic manner, elements of traditional structure with a view to improving skill levels, job independence, higher remuneration, active engagement and sustenance of interest of all stakeholders.

Adoga and Ohajionu, (2021) examined Igbo Apprenticeship System, anchored on the Theory of Experiential Learning (TEL), can enhance the effectiveness of entrepreneurship education and practice in Nigeria and other emerging economies. The research design/approach adopted in this study is the Model approach for designing conceptual studies. This approach involves identifying new connections between phenomena, building of theoretical propositions that uncover new constructs and/or connections between constructs, and explaining the reason behind the outcome from a sequence of events. A functional and viable entrepreneurial development system with almost a century-long evidence of job and wealth creation exists to address critical macroeconomic issues such as rising unemployment, widespread poverty and economic stagnation. The proposed adapted IAS significantly reduces rate of startup failures, increases rate of business startups and ultimately, facilitates national economic growth and development. These arguments are not simply based on the observable evidence of the socioeconomic impact of the IAS among the Igbo ethnic group, but also on grounded theory of learning (Experiential Learning Theory) and emerging evidences from empirical studies in entrepreneurship education and practice.

Godwin and Egboh (2021) examined skill acquisition and entrepreneurship development programmes and reduction in youth unemployment in Nigeria. The study concludes that despite the avalanche of programmes being initiated and introduced by government and even the private sector in Nigeria in terms of skill acquisition and entrepreneurship among youths in particular that youth unemployment rate continues to soar. The efficacy of skill acquisition and entrepreneurship to tackle this menace has been constrained by factors such as neglect of rural areas in skill acquisition programmes, poor funding by government, inadequacy of training infrastructures, epileptic power supply, unfavourable fiscal policies,

difficulty in accessing of funds, and quality of skill acquisition training and importantly the attitude of participants. All these needs redress.

METHODOLOGY

Survey research design was adopted in this study. The choice of survey method is that it is cost effective, dependable and a true representation of the entire population. The sources of data in this study were comprise the primary and secondary sources. The population for the study comprised of all the boss who has been in the business from 5 years upwards, the study will choose three market from the three senatorial zones In Anambra state which is Nnewi spare parts markets, (1,467) Onitsha main market, (1,545) staff. Eke Awka (1200). This gave a total of 4212 population. The sample size for this study was determined by using the Borg & Gall formular of (1973). Statistically, the Borg & Gall (1973) formular. Given the nature of this study, it was difficult to cover the entire population of (4212), so a fair representative sample of the population therefore was considered imperative. Accordingly, the sample size for the study was determined by using the Borg & Gall (1973) formular for calculating sample size as 809. The instrument use for data collection was questionnaire. The adopted content validity because we were able to cover all the relevant characteristics of the study theme. The reliability of the instrument was maintained through the test-retest method. and spearman’s rank correlation coefficient. The coefficient of reliability was found to be high, $R_s=0.79394$. This indicates a strong and positive correlation therefore, the research instrument was adjudged as being reliable. Statistics such as frequency count and percentages was put to use in the analysis of research questions while hypotheses was tested using Analysis of variance (ANOVA) analysis. The hypotheses was tested at 0.05 level of significance. Analysis was carried out with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Decision rule: We will accept H_0 , if p-value is greater than 5% level of significance, otherwise we will reject H_0 , to accept H_1

PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF DATA

Eight hundred and nine (909) were administered, among the successful and highly educated Igbo traders in Nnewi spare parts markets in Anambra state and its environs. However, seven hundred and forty-two (742) questionnaires were retrieved. Therefore the analysis and interpretation of data were only based on the returned questionnaire. The validity and reliability of this study is highly ensured, despite the number of questionnaire not returned.

4.2 Demographic characteristics of Respondent

Table 4.2.1 Status

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Married	326	40.5	43.9	43.9
	Single	141	17.5	19.0	62.9
	Widowed	129	16.0	17.4	80.3
	Divorced	72	8.9	9.7	90.0
	Separated	74	9.2	10.0	100.0
	Total	742	92.2	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2024

The above table reveals that the three hundred and twenty-six (326) of the respondents which represents 43.9% were married, while one hundred and forty-one (141) respondents which represent 19.0% were single. Again, one hundred and twenty-nine (129) of the respondents which represents 17.4% were

widowed, seventy-two (72) of the respondents which represent 9.7% were divorced in our selected population sample for this study. Lastly, seventy-four (74) respondent which represent 10% were separated The implication of this is to enable us to know the number of married, single, divorced and widowed respondents that successfully returned their questionnaire.

Table 4.2.1 There are benefits associated with seed capital financing relative to bank loans

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	A	308	38.3	41.5	41.5
	SA	280	34.8	37.7	79.2
	D	45	5.6	6.1	85.3
	SD	65	8.1	8.8	94.1
	U	44	5.5	5.9	100.0
	Total	742	92.2	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2024

The table above indicates that three hundred and eight (308) respondents which representing 41.5% agreed that there are benefits associated with seed capital financing (from the Igbo apprenticeship scheme) relative to bank loans, while 37.7% of the respondents which represents two hundred and eighty (280) strongly agreed to that. Forty-five (45) respondents which represent 6.1% are strongly disagreed. Sixty-five (65) respondents which represent 8.8% were of the view that disagreed. Forty-four (44) respondents which represent 5.9% strongly disagree finally; forty-four (44) respondents which represent 5.9% were undecided.

Table 4.2.2 Seed capital financing increased the sales revenue by greater magnitudes

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	A	455	56.5	61.3	61.3
	SA	169	21.0	22.8	84.1
	D	69	8.6	9.3	93.4
	SD	18	2.2	2.4	95.8
	U	31	3.9	4.2	100.0
	Total	742	92.2	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2024

The table above indicates that four hundred and fifty-five (455) respondents which representing 61.3% agreed that Seed capital financing increased the sales revenue by greater magnitudes, while 22.8% of the respondents which represents one hundred and sixty-nine (169) agreed to that. Sixty-nine (69) respondents which represent 9.3% are disagreed. Eighteen (18) respondents which represent 2.4% were of the view that disagreed. Finally, thirty-one (31) respondents which represent 4.2% were undecided.

Table 4.2.3 Seed capital reduces in business costs was experienced

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	A	323	40.1	43.5	43.5
	SA	236	29.3	31.8	75.3
	D	54	6.7	7.3	82.6
	SD	63	7.8	8.5	91.1
	U	66	8.2	8.9	100.0
	Total	742	92.2	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2024

The table above indicates that three hundred and twenty-three (323) respondents which representing 43.5% agreed that Seed capital reduces in business costs was experienced, while 31.8% of the respondents which represents two hundred and thirty-six (236) respondents strongly agreed to that. Fifty-four (54) respondents which represent 7.3% are disagreed. Whereas, sixty-three (63) respondents which represent 8.5 % were of the view that they strongly disagreed. Finally, sixty-six (66) respondents which represent 8.9% were undecided.

Table 4.2.4 Liquidity has improved since seed capital financing

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	A	232	28.8	31.3	31.3
	SA	310	38.5	41.8	73.0
	D	79	9.8	10.6	83.7
	SD	92	11.4	12.4	96.1
	U	29	3.6	3.9	100.0
	Total	742	92.2	100.0	

Source: SPSS Version 21, 2024

The table above indicates that two hundred and thirty-two (232) respondents which representing 31.3% agreed that liquidity, has improved with seed capital financing, while 41.8% of the respondents which represents thirty hundred and ten (310) strongly agreed to that. Seventy-nine (79) respondents which represent 10.6% are strongly disagreed. Ninety-two (92) respondents which represent 12.4% strongly disagreed. Finally, twenty-nine (29) respondents which represent 3.9% were undecided.

Multiple Regression Analysis

Multiple regression result was employed to test the effect of independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables. The result of the multiple regression analysis is presented in the tables below.

Summary of the Regression Result

The result of the multiple regressions formulated in chapter three is presented in the tables below.

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				Sig. Change	F Durbin-Watson
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2		
1	.673 ^a	.524	.513	.96254	.224	20.844	4	289	.000	1.820

a. Predictors: (Constant), ASA, SEC, ATS, MEN

b. Dependent Variable: EVS

The table shows that R² which measures the strength of the effect of independent variable on the dependent variable have the value of 52%. This implies that 52% of the variation in entrepreneurial development is explained by variations in seed capital, mentorship, and apprenticeship training skill. This was supported by adjusted R² of 51%. In order to check for autocorrelation in the model, Durbin-Watson statistics was employed. Durbin-Watson statistics of 1.820 in table 3 shows that the variables in the model are not auto correlated and that the model is reliable for predications.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	77.244	4	19.311	20.844	.000 ^b
	Residual	267.752	289	.926		
	Total	344.997	293			

a. Dependent Variable: EVS

b. Predictors: (Constant), ASA, SEC, , MEN

The f-statistics value of 20.844 in table 4.5 with f-statistics probability of 0.000 shows that the independent variables has significant effect on dependent variables such as apprenticeship skill acquisition, seed capital, apprenticeship training system, and mentorship can collectively explain the variations in top entrepreneurial development.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.050	.347		3.024	.003
	SEC	.262	.040	.351	6.512	.000
	MEN	.185	.067	.185	2.763	.006
	ATS	.215	.059	.230	3.657	.000
	ASA	.089	.056	.101	3.592	.000

a. Dependent Variable: EVS

A’p priori Criteria: This is determined by the existing business theories; it also indicates the signs and magnitude of the business parameter under review. In table 4.3.3 above, we found out that seed capital (SEC) has a positive sign given its value as 0.262 this implies that a unit increase in seed capital (SEC) increases the entrepreneurial development by 26.2%, this conform to the a’ priori expectation. Mentorship (MEN) has a positive sign and its value is 0.18% this implies that a unit increase in Mentorship (MEN) increases the entrepreneurial development by 18%, this also conforms to theoretical expectations. Apprenticeship training system (ATS) has a positive sign and its value as 0.215; this implies that a unit increases in Apprenticeship training system (ATS) increase the entrepreneurial venture success by .215%; this conforms to a’ priori expectation.

Test of Hypotheses

Here, the four hypotheses formulated in chapter one was tested using t-statistics and significance value of the individual variables in the regression result. The essence of this is to ascertain how significant are the effect of individual independent or explanatory variables on the dependent variables.

Hypothesis One

H₀: Seed capital has no significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

H₁: Seed capital has a significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

Seed capital has a t-statistics of 6.512 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that Seed capital has a significant effect on venture success in Anambra State.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: Mentorship has no significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

H₁: Mentorship has no significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

In testing this hypothesis, the t-statistics and probability value in table 4.3.3 above is used. Mentorship variables have a t-statistics of 2.763 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Mentorship has significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

Hypothesis Three

H₀: Apprenticeship training system has no significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

H₁: Apprenticeship training system has no significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

Apprenticeship training system has a t-statistics of 3.657 and a probability value of 0.000 which is statistically significant. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that Apprenticeship training system has significant effect on venture success in Anambra State

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

This research examined the effect of Apprenticeship in Igbo land on venture success in Anambra State. Data were sourced from the operators/owners of the selected firm. The data generated were subjected to statistical analysis and the following output was ascertained.

Seed capital and Entrepreneurial Development: The study found that Seed capital has significant positive effect on venture success. This implies that improved Seed capital would translate to increased venture success. It increases output and participation in the apprenticeship programme thereby enhancing business output. The seed capital is an institutional effort aimed at helping an apprentice in training to acquire enough start-up for the efficient execution of the function for which he is expected in the business.

Mentorship and venture success: The study found that mentorship has a significant positive effect on venture success of selected businesses. This implies that mentorship provide motivation and propel apprentice in training to behave in ways that would lead to enhanced productivity. Alfandi and Alkhasawneh (2014) found that enriched mentorship is a significant factor that encourages entrepreneurial venture success which results in enhanced productivity and performance.

Apprenticeship training system and venture success: Training can be described as a form of teaching and/or practice application in the realm of development of skills. The study found that Apprenticeship training system has a significant positive effect on Entrepreneurial Development. The implication of these findings is that, for an entrepreneurial venture success to be functional to achieve their aim and purposes, the Apprenticeship training system need to satisfy the expected needs of the individual, and must be seen to be fair or equitably satisfying to the apprentice in training. This further agreed with the findings of Iyida (2015), who found that increase in apprenticeship training system enhances the entrepreneurial venture success. The findings also corroborate with the findings of Olatunji and Sarat (2014) that Apprenticeship training system are pertinent determinant to venture success in Anambra state

Summary of the Findings

From the analysis of the data especially, and the testing of hypothesis it was realized that:

However, the research study also made the following specific findings;

1. Seed capital has significant effect on venture success in Anambra State (t-test, 6.512, p-0.000).
2. Mentorship has significant effect on venture success in Anambra State.(t-test 2.763, p0.000).
3. Apprenticeship training system has significant effect on venture success in Anambra State (t-test, 3.657,p-0.000).

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that apprenticeship in Igbo Land had a positive significance effect on venture success in Anambra State, Nigeria, Besides the readily available seed capital for business to start, Igbo apprenticeship programme enhance continuity in the pre-settlement business training and experience, because of ready-made shops and the existing customers which serve as a ready market for the apprentice that are settled with that approach. The approach has advantage of stock and location; it also helps in breeding new entrepreneurs. It is obvious and clearly stated that, new entrepreneurs will emerge with pre-settlement business training and experience and the case of leaving the business to start another one is minimized with this method. It is therefore a necessary subject of contention to fashion-out the modus operandi of encouraging the compensation-tied apprenticeship scheme that will see to the success of the method and as such vicious circle of poverty will be reduced in Nigeria economy. This method will serve as a compliment to programmes of government like, Poverty Alleviation Programme and Poverty Eradication Programme since unemployment case in Nigeria is a multi-dimensional in nature and as such need multi-disciplinary cure/solution and approach.

From the review of the Igbo apprenticeship scheme (IAS), it is clear that the system provides a proven model which can be adopted, adapted and integrated as the practice component of entrepreneurship education programme, so as to improve the outcomes of these programmes, leading to job and wealth creation as well as growth and development of Nigeria and other countries in Africa. Adopting the

proposed adapted Igbo apprentice scheme (IAS) as the practice component of entrepreneurship education programme in Nigeria and other emerging economies will significantly reduce rates of startup business failures, increase number of successful startups, enable greater number of job creation and catalyze general economic growth and development in Nigeria and in other developing countries.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. There is need for adequate regulations on the seed capital for the Igbo apprenticeship system by involving government and financial institutions. There should be more regulations in this scheme to provide adequate legal framework to guide and regulate the scheme.
2. Stakeholders should equally support successfully graduated apprentices to gain a foothold in their new business by providing more training and finance to establish more business and entrepreneurial ventures instead of looking for paid and salaried employment.
3. For small business sustainability, apprentices should continually undergo more appropriate traditional and formal business training to obtain necessary skills and experiences. Government and educational institutions should make the scheme formal by incorporating it into school and educational curriculum.

Contribution to Knowledge

The study examined the Apprenticeship in Igbo land on venture success in Anambra State. Findings from the study revealed that the Igbo apprenticeship system (IAS) through its seed capital provision, mentorship and apprenticeship training have positive and significant impact on the economic development in Nigeria. By implication, the apprenticeship system has contributed in no small way to the development, improvement and sustenance of the economy through business creations and stable human development index.

REFERENCES

- Adekola, G. (2013) Traditional Apprenticeship in the Old Africa and Its Relevance to Contemporary Work Practices in Modern Nigerian Communities. *British Journal of Education, Society & Behavioural Science* 3(4): 397-406,
- Agozino, B., & Anyanike, I. (2017). Imu-Ahia: Traditional Igbo business school and global commerce. *Culture, Dialectical Anthropology* 58: 1301–1328.
- Allen, T. D. (2017). *Mentoring relationships from the perspective of the mentor*. In B. R. Ragins & K. E. Kram (Eds.). *The handbook of mentoring at Work: Theory, Research and practice* (Pp. 123–147). Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage Publication
- Ayodo, I. A., Namusonge, G. S., & Mbithi, S. M. (2021) Influence of career mentoring practices on employee job satisfaction of academic staff in Public Universities in Kenya. *Strategic Journal of Business & Change Management*, 8(1), 845 – 862
- Brockbank, A., & McGill, I. (2016). *Facilitating reflective learning through mentoring and coaching*. London and Philadelphia: Kogan Page.
- Cherono, V., Towett, D. K. and Njeje, D. (2016) Influence of Mentorship Practices on Employee Performance in Small Manufacturing Firms in Garissa County, Kenya. *European Journal of Business and Management* 8(8), 151-160
- Cherono, V., Towett, D. K., Njeje, D. (2016). Influence of Mentorship Practices on Employee Performance in Small Manufacturing Firms in Garissa country, Kenya // *European Journal of Business and Management*. 8, (8) 151–160.
- Chinweuba, G. E. & Ezenwa, E. C. (2017). The ontological foundation of Igbo entrepreneurship an analytical investigation, *Journal of Philosophy, Culture and Religion*, 33 17-24.
- Colky, D. L., & Young, W. H. (2016). *Mentoring in the virtual organization: Keys to building successful schools and businesses*. Mentoring & Tutoring

- Diyoke, C. I. (2014). Entrepreneurship development in Nigeria: issues, problems and prospects. *International Journal of Technical Research and Applications*, 10 (Nov-Dec), 19-23.
- Ejo-Orusa, H. (2019) Reinventing the 'nwaboi' apprenticeship system: a platform for entrepreneurship promotion in Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Management and Social Sciences* 8(9)98-1110
- Ekesiobi, C. and Dimnwobi, S. K. (2020) : Economic assessment of the Igbo entrepreneurship model for entrepreneurial development in Nigeria: Evidence from clusters in Anambra State, AGDI Working Paper, No. WP/20/085, African Governance and Development Institute (AGDI), Yaoundé.
- Gamage, K. A. A.; Perera, D .A. S.; Wijewardena, M. A. D. N. (2021) Mentoring and Coaching as a Learning Technique in Higher Education: The Impact of Learning Context on Student Engagement in Online Learning. *Journal of Education. Science*, 11, 574.
- Kanu, I. A. (2019). Igwebuik economics: The Igbo apprenticeship system for wealth creation, *African Journal of Arts and Humanities* 5 (4),56-70.
- Napolitano, C. S., & Henderson, L. J. (2020). *The Leadership Odyssey: A Self- Development Guide to New Skills for New Times*. San Francisco, CA: Jossey-Bass.
- Ndung'u, C. N. (2016) The effect of mentoring on employee career success in Nairobi's Star Rated Hotels. Department of Business Administration of University Of Nairobi.
- Nzewi, H. N., Onwuka, E. M. & Onyesom, M. (2017). Entrepreneurship evolution and the growth of small scale businesses in Nigeria. *Journal of Business and Economic Development*. 2(3), 176-181
- Okumu, J. B., Ogwang, T. H., & Wafula, W. S. (2021). Mentoring and Teacher Effectiveness in Government-Aided Secondary Schools in the Acholi Sub Region in Uganda. *Creative Education*, 12, 2700-2714.
- Olulu, R. M. & Udeorah, S. A. F. (2018). Contract of apprenticeship and employment generation in Nigeria. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 1(3), 335-344
- Olusegun, F. L. & Olanrewaju, A. O. (2017). Traditional Apprenticeship, Normative Expectations and Sustainability o Masonry Vocation in Ibadan, Nigeria. *International Journal of Sociology of Education*, 6(2), 186-215.
- Orogbu, L. O., Onyeizugbe, C. U. Onuzulike-Chukwuemeka, N. F (2021) "Apprenticeship and Entrepreneurship Development among Igbo Traders in Nigeria" Published in *International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development* 5(6), 999-1007
- Toor, S., & Ofori, G. (2018). Leadership for future construction industry: Agenda for authentic leadership. *International Journal of Project Management*, 26, 620-630
- Udom, I. D., Okoedion, E. S. and Okolie, U. C. (2020) Impact of mentorship on students' academic excellence in University of Benin, Benin City. *Journal of plus education* 25(1), 211 228
- Yankov, L., & Kleiner, B. H. (2011). Human resources issues in the construction industry. *Management Research News*, 24(3/4), 101-105
- Obananya, C. G. (2022). Entrepreneurship and rural development in Anambra State. *Journal of Research in Business and Management* 10 79-86
- Eze, S. U. Muogbo, U. & Obananya, C.G.(2021). Business Mentoring and Entrepreneurship